

An Electrometric Study on the Quantitative Precipitation of Yttrium(III) as Normal Chromate

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Among the methods for the determination of yttrium in traces, reported in the literature¹⁻¹⁷, the chromate ion has been successfully used in the microdetermination¹⁸ of lanthanum, samarium, and neodymium. The present communication deals with the determination of yttrium as its normal chromate by conductometric titrations under varied experimental conditions.

Procedure.—A. R. potassium chromate (B.D.H.) and yttrium oxide (A.R., Atomic Energy Establishment, Trombay) were used. Yttrium oxide was dissolved in A.R. nitric acid and evaporated for crystallisation. The crystals were dissolved in conductivity water and recrystallised thrice to remove excess of nitric acid. Potassium chromate and yttrium nitrate were dissolved separately in conductivity water. Yttrium was estimated as Y_2O_3 and chromate as Cr_2O_7 and also volumetrically. Solutions of desired concentrations were prepared by appropriate dilution.

Conductometric titrations were carried out on Philips conductivity bridge, type PR9500, 220V a. c. line-operated, direct-reading electronic instrument with an electron-beam indicator for the balance. The titrations were carried out at different ethanol concentrations ranging from 0 to 50%, as a correct end point could not be obtained in aqueous medium. A 35% ethanol concentration provided the best results.

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Direct Conductometric Titrations.—A known volume of yttrium nitrate solution with an overall 35% ethanol was taken in a 100-ml Pyrex beaker, placed on a magnetic stirrer; the cell was dipped properly and the initial conductance recorded. Potassium chromate solution was added from a micro-burette in small amounts, the mixture stirred well and the readings were recorded after allowing the precipitate to settle. The end point was obtained graphically by plotting volume of the titrant added against the corrected conductance.

Reverse Conductometric Titrations.—In the reverse titration, a known volume of potassium chromate solution containing 35% ethanol by volume was taken in the beaker and yttrium nitrate solution added from the micro-burette; the rest of the procedure was the same as in the case of direct titrations.

Yttrium nitrate solutions at concentrations between $1.804 \times 10^{-4} M$ and $5.772 \times 10^{-4} M$ were successfully titrated with $0.024929 M$ potassium chromate. In the reverse titrations potassium chromate solutions (4.154×10^{-4} to $8.303 \times 10^{-4} M$) were titrated with yttrium nitrate solution of $0.02163 M$.

The direct conductometric titration curves show only one sharp end point of intersection corresponding to the formation of normal yttrium chromate; the reaction involved in the titration can be represented as:

In direct titrations, the conductance increases up to the equivalence point which is due to replacement of less mobile Y^{3+} ions by more mobile K^+ ions. In post equivalence region, the conductance increases rapidly due to the excess of K^+ and CrO_4^{2-} ions added.

In reverse titrations, excess of potassium chromate is present initially and when yttrium nitrate solution is gradually added to potassium chromate solution, the conductance decreases very slowly, probably due to the formation of normal yttrium chromate and an immediate adsorption of potassium chromate on it. In post equivalence region, the conductance increases very rapidly, which is due to the addition of yttrium nitrate in excess.

Thus the procedure affords a convenient means for the titrimetric determination of yttrium on a microscale.

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